

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th August 2023

Accepted: 25th August 2023

Online: 26th August 2023

KEY WORDS

Partonage, oncology patient, safe and dangerous tumors, recurrence, metastasis, professional responsibility, professional ethics.

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE NURSE'S ACTIVITY IN CARRYING OUT PATRONAGE OF ONCOLOGICAL PATIENTS

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8285696>

ABSTRACT

In this article, instructions are given on patronage nursing service in oncological diseases, duties of nurses, professional responsibility and professional ethics of carrying out patronage of oncological patients.

Introduction. Patronage service is a type of dispensary control, which is carried out for the purpose of active examination of the population at home and preventive examination of certain groups of the healthy population. In most cases, patronage is carried out by an obstetrician-gynecologist, pediatrician and general practitioner among pregnant women, newborns or children under 3 years old. Thanks to patronage control, mortality and complications among pregnant women and children are reduced.

As a result of the creation of the patronage service, the volume of medical and preventive work will be expanded, the conditions for maintaining apartments will be improved, the return of patients to work will be improved, and susceptibility to infections will be reduced.

Patronage in oncological diseases is a treatment and prophylactic method. Preventive patronage for oncological patients in I "A" and III clinical stages (presumptive diagnosis of the tumor and under control after treatment), I "B", II and IV clinical stages (precancerous diseases and preserved tumors that received radical treatment and diseases). service for the treatment of missed patients). Among oncologists, the decision of this issue lies with the district oncologists. They perform the tasks of admitting patients to a specialized oncological hospital and treating it on an outpatient basis, identifying precancerous diseases and conducting timely examination methods, as well as monitoring patients after treatment.

Paying attention to a malignant tumor by an oncologist during patronage of oncological patients is of great importance. All oncology patients, after being systematically treated by an oncologist, undergo a patronage examination and check-up every quarter of the first year, every 6 months of the second year, and once a year starting from the third year. In this case, the patient should be excluded from relapses and metastases.

A patronage nurse is the closest assistant of a doctor-oncologist in carrying out patronage and treatment of an oncological patient. The patronage nurse takes the oncology patient to the dispensary and monitors his condition, regularly monitors the treatment and treatment processes and is by his side. It should be said that the patient's mental experiences with stage IV metastasis (spread of cancer to all organs) also have an effect on the nurse.

Duties of the patronage nurse. The patronage nurse not only supervises patients, but also performs the following tasks:

- prepares the oncologist's room for patient reception, files patients' documents, sterilizes vision equipment, sends cytological examination materials to the laboratory;
- participates in the organization of preventive examinations of the population and conducts sanitary-propaganda work among people;
- actively participates as a mediator in hospitalization of the patient and as a key worker in outpatient treatment.

During the work of the oncologist doctor, he prepares the work schedule for the patronage nurse, gives him explanations and monitors his work. Two situations are important in the work of a patronage nurse in oncology:

1. The patronage nurse, under the guidance of the oncologist, independently decides many things and takes responsibility;
2. He decides the relationship with a serious oncological patient by himself without the help of a doctor.

A nurse should demonstrate professionalism in dealing with the patient, fully communicating the diagnosis and keeping the outcome confidential. In most cases, it depends on the general and medical culture of the patronage nurse, the breadth of his worldview and the feeling of sympathy for the patient. Such a feature should be characteristic of a patronage nurse. Therefore, it is desirable for a patronage nurse to have special training in the field of oncology and to know some information perfectly. For example:

- to have information about safe and dangerous tumors;
- good knowledge of methods of examination and treatment of oncological diseases;
- knowledge of precancerous diseases and their treatment methods;
- to be aware of the diagnosis and treatment methods of dangerous and safe tumors of the female genital organs;
- should have knowledge about dispensary of oncological diseases.

In oncology, the practice requirements for a patronage nurse are defined as follows:

- Providing information about oncological diseases, care of patients undergoing radical and palliative treatment;
- To work with other organizations in taking into account oncological diseases in regional polyclinics and fighting against cancer;
- Patient registration and awareness of disease indicators;
- To know the clinical classification of oncological diseases, to carry out patronage accordingly.

The patronage nurse should be average, free from excessive decorations, well-dressed, clean-headed, and make a good impression on patients. He should treat the patient politely, considerately and perform the given task carefully.

The responsibility of correctly assessing the patient's condition, understanding his mental state and establishing the right attitude should be reflected in the character of the patronage nurse. The nurse should appear in the eyes of the patient and his relatives as a selfless example of prolonging the patient's life. More specifically, a patronage nurse is an employee who actively participates in the treatment and prevention of oncological diseases, organizational work, advocacy and patient psychotherapy.

Conclusion. Professional responsibility and love for one's work are the main criteria in patronage nursing. In particular, patronage is the main one among the above-mentioned tasks of promotion and advocacy in nursing activities. One of the things to be done in this direction is to inculcate in people's minds that the correct treatment of oncological diseases in the early stages will eliminate the development of dangerous tumors.

So, in order to be able to fulfill the great task of a patronage nurse serving in the field of oncology, it is necessary to work tirelessly on oneself, study and be responsible.

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